

Enhancing Resilience and Addressing Vulnerability through Risk Communication in Waste Management: Tackling Landfill Fires and Disaster Risks in Serbia

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Extended abstract: Waste management in Serbia is characterized by numerous challenges, risks, and threats to both public safety and the environment. Preliminary analyses have identified a range of issues that are directly or indirectly related to the following: a) non-selective waste separation; b) inadequate facilities for safe waste disposal; c) numerous and prolonged landfill fires that release toxic substances (dioxins, furans, etc.); d) lack of sanitary landfills; e) improper treatment of industrial waste; f) landslides and contamination of groundwater; g) insufficient oversight and control; h) low levels of environmental awareness and citizen engagement; i) lack of recycling infrastructure; j) inadequate funding and investment in waste management; k) illegal waste disposal and the prevalence of unauthorized landfills; l) poor energy utilization of

waste; m) insufficient integration of circular economy principles; n) issues related to medical waste management; o) lack of data transparency in waste management; and p) non-compliance with EU directives and delays in the adoption of waste management strategies.

Given these challenges, the scientific and societal justification for this research is immense, as there is an urgent need for comprehensive reforms in waste management systems, infrastructure, and oversight. The scope of this research is underscored by the existence of over 3,500 illegal dumpsites, the generation of more than 8.2 million tons of industrial waste annually, of which approximately 7.9 million tons is non-hazardous. However, only 19% of this waste is properly recycled, while on the other hand, only 5% of municipal waste is recycled.

According to data from the Republic Statistical Office, a total of 174.7 million tons of waste was generated in 2022 alone, with the mining sector being the largest contributor, whereas municipal waste represents a smaller portion of the total waste volume. Annually, approximately 2.4 million tons of municipal waste is collected across Serbia, yet one-third of the population is not covered by an organized waste collection system, suggesting that the actual volume of municipal waste is likely even higher. In terms of waste treatment, data from 2019 indicate that 96.4% of collected waste was simply disposed of without any treatment. While Serbia's regulatory framework includes waste management laws aligned with EU standards, their implementation remains inadequate.

One of the largest landfills in Serbia, Vinča, has caught fire multiple times, with major incidents occurring in 2017, 2019, and 2020. The most severe fire happened in 2017, when approximately 20 hectares of landfill burned, releasing thick smoke that spread across large parts of Belgrade. Similarly, in 2024, the Duboko landfill near Užice burned for nearly three weeks, causing severe air contamination. In April 2024, a fire at a landfill in Temerin released toxic substances into the atmosphere, further highlighting the risks associated with inadequate waste management. These incidents have demonstrated the urgent need for research to determine how enhanced risk communication can contribute to increasing the resilience of local communities and reducing their vulnerability to future waste-related disasters.

Residents living near landfills are frequently exposed to various forms of soil and water contamination, which contributes to an increase in respiratory diseases, allergic reactions, and other health problems. Furthermore, citizens do not receive timely and adequate information about potential risks and hazards, indicating a lack of transparency in communication between institutions and the public. Persistent unpleasant odors, environmental degradation, and

uncertainty contribute to stress, anxiety, and feelings of helplessness among affected communities. Moreover, they do not receive timely recommendations, guidelines, or instructions on how to protect themselves or respond in such situations. In practice, there is also a discrepancy between the official data released by government institutions and the actual situation on the ground, leading to speculation and the spread of misinformation. Ultimately, the demands of local communities for improvements are ignored, public discussions are lacking, property values near landfills decline, agricultural income is lost, and healthcare costs for the local population continue to rise. Based on the identified problems, high levels of vulnerability, and low resilience of local communities, a quantitative study was conducted across nine local communities in Serbia: Čačak, Užice, Požega, Lučani, Kosjerić, Čajetina, Bajina Bašta, Ivanjica, and Arilje.

The research was carried out using multi-stage random sampling within these communities. To facilitate the study, a survey questionnaire was developed to assess citizens' perceptions of environmental issues and waste management practices. Prior to the main research, a pilot study was conducted to ensure the validity of the measurement scales. The questionnaire covers various aspects of the problem, including demographic and socio-economic characteristics of respondents, their environmental awareness, level of concern about potential risks, and trust in institutions and their communication with the public. Specifically, it collects demographic information such as gender, age group, education level, and place of residence.

Additionally, it evaluates citizens' concerns about the environmental impact of landfills on air, soil, and water quality, as well as the long-term health consequences associated with poor waste management. A key focus of the study was the sense of control over the situation—whether citizens believe they can contribute to solving waste management problems and whether they feel they have the ability to influence decisions made by relevant institutions. The study also examined trust in local and national authorities, environmental inspectors, and scientific institutions regarding waste management and landfill-related issues. Another critical aspect analyzed was the transparency of institutions—whether citizens consider environmental risk information to be accessible and reliable and how satisfied they are with media coverage of these issues. The lack of information and transparency was identified as a significant factor affecting public trust and willingness to engage in problem-solving initiatives. Furthermore, the study explored the extent to which citizens support environmental organizations and civic initiatives that address waste management

issues. Finally, it assessed citizens' willingness to support waste reduction initiatives and efforts to improve environmental conditions in their communities.

The research findings indicate that respondents exhibit a high level of concern about environmental problems, particularly in relation to air, soil, and water pollution resulting from inadequate waste management. The majority of participants perceive landfills as a long-term risk to public health and the environment, while also expressing a strong sense of powerlessness in addressing these issues. The study revealed that citizens generally feel they lack control over environmental decision-making and have little confidence in their ability to influence institutional actions. The implications of this research are significant for waste management policies, environmental regulations, risk communication strategies, and citizen participation in decision-making. The results highlight the urgent need for more transparent governance, improved communication between institutions and the public, and the development of policies that empower communities to take an active role in environmental protection and sustainable waste management.